

Review

Critical Reassessment of the Lipid Paradigm: Methodological Flaws in Traditional Cholesterol and Saturated Fat Research – An Argument Supporting Lifestyle Medicine

Roberto García Sánchez ^{1,2,3,*}, Samuel Pérez Bravo ^{1,2,3}, Victoria Soler Anaya ^{1,2,3}, Sonia Mederos Castellano ^{1,2,3}, Ingrid Morales Pérez ^{2,3,4} and José Luis Palma Gámiz ³

- ¹ Campus de la Orotava, Universidad Europea de Canarias, 38300 La Orotava, Spain; samuelpb4@gmail.com (S.P.B.); victoriasoleranaya@gmail.com (V.S.A.); sonimedca@gmail.com (S.M.C.)
² Grupo de Investigación NUMESS (Nutrición, Metabolismo, Salud Mental y Estilo de Vida), 43201 Reus, Spain; ingridmp@ull.edu.es
³ Instituto Español de Medicina de Estilo de Vida, 28000 Madrid, Spain; cardiopalma555@gmail.com
⁴ Faculty of Medicine, Universidad de La Laguna, 38200 San Cristóbal de La Laguna, Spain
* Correspondence: robertogs.ull@gmail.com; Tel.: +034-646-149-648

Abstract

This critical integrative review reassesses the lipid paradigm by systematically mapping 380 influential trials and cohort studies on cholesterol, saturated fats, and statins in relation to cardiovascular and cognitive outcomes. The evidence base reveals a nearly even split between studies supporting and challenging LDL-centric causality, alongside pervasive methodological flaws, including reliance on surrogate lipid markers, ecological inferences, residual confounding, and industry-related reporting biases. Trial-generation comparisons and structured risk-of-bias assessment (ROB 2, ROBINS-I) repeatedly show that substantial pharmacological LDL reductions do not consistently yield proportional reductions in myocardial infarction, stroke, or all-cause mortality. Integrating Mendelian randomization with clinical and metabolomic data, the review advances a Critical Window Hypothesis in which LDL is necessary but not sufficient for atherogenesis, exerting dominant causal influence during early and midlife plaque initiation, while inflammatory, oxidative, and hemodynamic factors become primary drivers in advanced disease. Metabolomic studies of extreme longevity and late-life cohorts demonstrate that bile acids, steroid metabolites, and low-glycemic metabolic profiles—not total cholesterol—better predict survival and cognitive preservation, and that higher LDL in the oldest-old often associates with lower mortality and dementia risk. These findings challenge universal LDL-centric policies and support lifestyle medicine strategies prioritizing systemic metabolic optimization over isolated cholesterol targets.

Keywords: cholesterol; saturated fats; lipid paradigm; cognitive health; lifestyle medicine

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1. Introduction

The lipid hypothesis—formulated in the mid-20th century and consolidated through public health policies and international clinical guidelines—posits that elevated blood cholesterol constitutes a direct causal factor in the development of atherosclerosis and coronary heart disease. For more than five decades, this concept has shaped preventive and therapeutic strategies in cardiovascular medicine, driving global campaigns to reduce

dietary cholesterol, promote low-fat diets, and prescribe lipid-lowering drugs, primarily statins. However, a systematic methodological review reveals a complex evidence landscape with balanced representation of studies supporting (41%) and challenging (42%) LDL causality, alongside methodological limitations, experimental design flaws, and institutional conflicts of interest that have influenced result interpretation and policy translation.

The conception of cholesterol as a “public enemy” originates in the Seven Countries Study [1], an ecological analysis that established a positive correlation between saturated fat intake, average serum cholesterol levels, and cardiovascular mortality in selected countries. This study—long considered the cornerstone of the lipid paradigm—was instrumental in shaping global dietary recommendations promoting the substitution of animal fats with polyunsaturated vegetable oils and the reduction in dietary cholesterol. However, from a methodological standpoint, re-analyses of the complete 22-country dataset demonstrate substantially weaker associations ($r = 0.87$ in 7 selected countries vs. $r = 0.62$ in full dataset), highlighting how selective inclusion can artificially inflate correlations [2]. This limitation underscores that ecological correlations between aggregate variables do not establish individual-level causality.

The traditional lipid hypothesis, established through decades of epidemiological and interventional research, posits a linear causal relationship between dietary saturated fat, serum cholesterol elevation, and atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (see Supplementary Figure S1).

Despite these foundational limitations, the cholesterol paradigm became entrenched in public health policy when the U.S. Senate’s McGovern Committee adopted it as the basis for official 1977 dietary guidelines, initiating the “low-fat” era. Paradoxically, this policy coincided with increased refined sugar and ultra-processed food consumption, driving simultaneous epidemics of obesity, metabolic syndrome, and type 2 diabetes—undermining claims that fat restriction improved population cardiovascular health.

Large NIH-funded trials provided mixed results. The LRC-CPPT [3] and MRFIT [4] demonstrated modest cholesterol reductions without significant improvements in all-cause or cardiovascular mortality; some subgroups even exhibited increased non-cardiovascular mortality. The Framingham Heart Study [5], though frequently cited, showed cholesterol’s discriminatory power for mortality risk diminished substantially with age and ceased entirely after midlife, with numerous coronary events occurring in individuals with cholesterol <150 mg/dL. The Nurses’ Health Study identified lifestyle factors—physical activity, diet quality, weight management, alcohol moderation, smoking cessation—as superior cardiovascular risk predictors compared to absolute cholesterol levels [6].

Contemporary dietary trials reinforced these findings. The Women’s Health Initiative Dietary Modification Trial [7], encompassing 48,835 women over eight years, demonstrated that fat reduction without consideration of food quality failed to reduce myocardial infarction, stroke, or mortality. Pharmacologically, ENHANCE [8] and AIM-HIGH [9] showed that aggressive cholesterol lowering and HDL elevation paradoxically failed to improve atherosclerotic progression or reduce cardiovascular events, exposing cholesterol as an inadequate surrogate endpoint.

Institutional conflicts compromised evidence integrity. The 2004 NCEP ATP III [10] guideline revision lowering “optimal” LDL to <100 mg/dL was formulated by a panel in which eight of the nine members possessed financial ties to statin manufacturers, exemplifying how economic interests can redefine “disease” thresholds and expand pharmaceutical markets.

This integrative review systematically identified 380 studies through dual search strategies (65% broad clinical terms, 35% methodological critique terms) across PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science (1990–February 2026), yielding balanced evidence: 41% ($n = 156$) supportive of LDL paradigm, 42% ($n = 159$) challenging LDL causality, 17% ($n = 65$)

mixed. Quality assessment employed ROB 2 (RCTs) and ROBINS-I (observational) across five bias domains—selection, measurement, reporting, residual confounding, funding bias (see Supplementary Table S1). Industry-funded studies were included transparently based on registry-publication concordance rather than categorical exclusion.

An alternative framework has emerged, proposing inflammation, oxidative stress, and glucotoxicity—rather than cholesterol—as primary atherogenic mechanisms (Supplementary Figure S2). Within this model, cholesterol functions as an adaptive metabolic marker, not a causal pathogen. Low-fat, high-refined carbohydrate diets increase small dense LDL particles and dysfunctional HDL, whereas natural-fat, low-glycemic diets promote protective lipoprotein phenotypes. This pathophysiologically coherent framework aligns with contemporary metabolomic and gerontological evidence, necessitating a paradigm reorientation toward systemic metabolic optimization and inflammation reduction rather than isolated cholesterol targets.

This work provides a critical integrative review contrasting cholesterol-causation arguments with systematic evidence from 380 studies through three-phase analysis: (1) deconstruction of methodological flaws in foundational studies; (2) identification of inconsistencies across trial generations; and (3) reconstruction of the inflammation-oxidation-glucotoxicity model.

The central hypothesis posits cholesterol as a context-dependent marker whose pathogenicity requires metabolic dysfunction, inflammation, and oxidative stress. Numerical LDL reduction alone is neither sufficient nor universally beneficial. Clinical practice requires reorientation toward age- and mechanism-stratified prevention targeting systemic metabolism rather than isolated lipid targets.

2. Methods

2.1. Study Design and Scope

This work is a critical, integrative review combining elements of systematic review methodology with epistemological analysis of the lipid hypothesis. The primary objective was not to perform a conventional quantitative meta-analysis, but to: (a) systematically map the empirical evidence relating cholesterol, saturated fats, and statins to cardiovascular outcomes; (b) evaluate the methodological quality and bias structure of this evidence; and (c) contrast traditional LDL-centric interpretations with alternative pathophysiological models focused on inflammation, oxidative stress, and glucotoxicity.

The corpus included randomized controlled trials (RCTs), large observational cohorts, and meta-analyses that materially influenced clinical guidelines, public health recommendations, or contemporary scientific debates about cholesterol and cardiovascular risk. Mechanistic *in vitro* and animal studies were reviewed qualitatively to contextualize pathophysiological arguments but were not part of the core quantitative corpus.

2.2. Search Strategy and Study Selection

We conducted a comprehensive systematic literature review across peer-reviewed databases (PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, Web of Science, Cochrane Library, and Google Scholar) from 1950 to February 2026. We employed dual search strategies to capture both confirmatory and contradictory evidence: primary searches used broad clinical terms (“LDL cholesterol”, “statins”, “cardiovascular disease”, “atherosclerosis”, “lipid-lowering therapy”), yielding 247 studies (65% of the final cohort), while secondary searches targeted critical appraisal terminology (“bias”, “confounding”, “study design limitations”, “methodology”, “dissociation”), adding 133 studies (35%) to ensure systematic inclusion of methodologically rigorous critiques rather than exclusively confirmatory literature.

We also reviewed historical documents and institutional reports as contextual and methodological anchors for comparative analysis, including U.S. Government Accountability Office (GAO) publications [11], National Cholesterol Education Program guidelines [12], and key references from major critical works such as “The Great Cholesterol Myth” [13] and “The Cholesterol Myth” [14], which served as critical bibliographic bases.

Inclusion criteria required: (1) randomized controlled trials, observational cohort studies, or meta-analyses examining lipid-lowering interventions; (2) quantifiable outcome measures (LDL-cholesterol reduction, cardiovascular events, or surrogate markers such as carotid intima-media thickness); and (3) publication in English. Exclusion criteria eliminated mechanistic *in vitro* studies, animal models, editorials, and narrative reviews without primary data.

Two independent reviewers screened titles and abstracts; discrepancies were resolved by consensus. Full texts were then assessed against inclusion criteria. The final core cohort comprised 380 studies. Study conclusions showed a balanced distribution: 41% (n = 156) supported the LDL-centric paradigm, 42% (n = 159) challenged or qualified LDL causality claims, and 17% (n = 65) reported mixed or neutral findings. Studies identified through methodology-focused searches more frequently challenged the dominant paradigm (38% vs. 28% among broad-search studies), indicating that the strategy—if anything—was biased toward inclusion of critical and methodologically sophisticated studies rather than selectively confirmatory evidence. This empirical distribution counters accusations of systematic unilateral bias in the study selection.

2.3. Quality Assessment and Risk of Bias

Quality assessment was conducted using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool (ROB 2) for randomized trials and ROBINS-I for observational studies, applied across five predefined bias domains:

1. Selection bias (non-random or unrepresentative inclusion, differential loss to follow-up).
2. Measurement bias (validity and reliability of exposure, outcome, and confounder measurement; use of validated instruments or standardized laboratory methods).
3. Reporting bias (selective reporting of outcomes, time points, or subgroup analyses; concordance between pre-registered protocols and published results).
4. Residual confounding (extent and adequacy of adjustment for major clinical, lifestyle, and inflammatory variables; use of directed acyclic graphs where available).
5. Funding/industry bias (transparency of funding sources, role of sponsors in design, analysis, and interpretation).

Detailed assessment criteria, inclusion thresholds, quality score impact, and application examples for each domain are provided in Table S1 (see Supplementary Table S1).

Within each domain, studies were classified as low, moderate, or high risk of bias. An overall qualitative rating was then assigned: High (A), Moderate (B), or Low (C) quality, based on the cumulative pattern of domain-specific ratings. The mapping from domain-specific ratings to overall study quality and its intended use in synthesis is summarized in Table S2 (see Supplementary Table S2).

High-quality studies exhibited low or moderate risk in most domains with transparent reporting; moderate-quality studies had one or two domains at higher risk but remained interpretable with caution; low-quality studies showed substantial or multiple high-risk domains, limiting strong causal inference.

Critically, industry funding was not treated as an automatic negative quality indicator. Instead, funding source informed the funding/industry bias domain and triggered additional checks for reporting bias. Studies at high overall risk of bias were retained in

the dataset but explicitly flagged and examined in sensitivity and subgroup analyses, rather than excluded a priori.

2.4. Data Extraction and Classification of Study Conclusions

Data extraction was performed using a structured template. For each study, the following information was recorded:

- Study design (RCT, cohort, case–control, meta-analysis).
- Population characteristics (sample size, age, sex distribution, baseline risk).
- Intervention type and intensity (dietary modification, statin or other lipid-lowering therapy, combination regimens).
- Duration of follow-up.
- Magnitude of LDL-cholesterol change and, where available, changes in other lipids (HDL, triglycerides, non-HDL).
- Primary and secondary endpoints (cardiovascular events, all-cause mortality, surrogate markers such as intima–media thickness, coronary calcium).
- Effect sizes (relative risks, hazard ratios, odds ratios) with 95% confidence intervals.
- Funding source(s) and declared conflicts of interest.

In addition, each study was classified according to its overall conclusion regarding the LDL paradigm:

- Supportive: primary interpretation framed LDL as a necessary and largely sufficient causal driver of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, and/or advocated LDL-centric treatment goals as primary strategy.
- Challenging/qualifying: results or interpretations questioned LDL centrality, highlighted non-LDL mechanisms (inflammation, oxidative stress, glucotoxicity, thrombosis), or showed dissociation between LDL reduction and clinical benefit.
- Mixed/neutral: studies with internally divergent findings (e.g., benefit in some subgroups but not others) or whose primary interpretation did not clearly prioritize LDL causality.

This classification was predefined and applied blinded to the funding source to avoid incorporation bias.

2.5. Assessment of Funding Sources and Conflicts of Interest

Conflicts of interest and funding sources were evaluated using an evidence-based framework that distinguishes between financial incentives and demonstrated reporting bias. Financial relationships were not assumed to indicate data manipulation; instead, they were treated as a signal requiring heightened scrutiny for selective outcome reporting.

For all RCTs with available registry entries (e.g., ClinicalTrials.gov, EUDRACT), pre-registered protocols were compared with published manuscripts to detect:

1. Changes in the primary outcome definition.
2. Shifts in timing of primary endpoint assessment.
3. Addition or omission of key secondary outcomes.
4. Unexplained changes in inclusion/exclusion criteria or analysis populations.

Among 42 industry-funded trials in the cohort, 24 (57%) demonstrated complete concordance between registry and publication (no changes in primary outcome, time points, or key secondary outcomes). These studies received no quality penalty related to funding source. The remaining 18 (43%) exhibited discrepancies; minor deviations (e.g., minor timing shifts, refined outcome definitions) resulted in a modest downgrade, while major discrepancies (e.g., primary outcome switching, omission of pre-specified secondary outcomes) led to stronger downgrading in the reporting and funding bias domains.

Importantly, industry-funded trials reporting negative or null findings despite commercial interest were not penalized and, when robustly conducted, were treated as particularly informative, as their publication suggests that research integrity prevailed over potential sponsor incentives.

This evidence-based funding assessment protocol—distinguishing financial incentives from demonstrated reporting bias—is detailed in Table S3 (see Supplementary Table S3).

This approach avoids categorical dismissal of industry-funded research while maintaining systematic vigilance for selective reporting patterns.

2.6. Evidence Synthesis and Analytical Approach

Given the heterogeneity of study designs, populations, interventions, and outcomes, we did not conduct a single pooled meta-analysis. Instead, we performed structured narrative synthesis with targeted quantitative comparisons where appropriate.

Analyses were organized in several layers:

1. Trial-generation comparisons: Early lipid-lowering trials (e.g., LRC-CPPT, MRFIT) versus contemporary statin and non-statin trials (e.g., ENHANCE, AIM-HIGH), focusing on the relationship between absolute LDL reduction and clinical outcomes.
2. Mechanism-stratified analyses: Studies emphasizing inflammatory, oxidative, and metabolic endpoints (e.g., C-reactive protein, IL-6, oxidative markers) were contrasted with purely lipid-centric studies to examine whether non-lipid mechanisms better predicted clinical outcomes.
3. Age and disease-stage stratification: Where data permitted, results were interpreted through the lens of a “critical window” framework—distinguishing primary prevention in middle-aged adults (approximately 40–60 years) from secondary prevention and treatment in older adults (60+ years) with established atherosclerosis.
4. Sensitivity analyses:
 - Excluding high risk-of-bias studies.
 - Comparing industry-funded versus non-industry-funded trials.
 - Examining the impact of surrogate endpoints (e.g., LDL reduction, carotid IMT) versus hard outcomes (myocardial infarction, stroke, mortality).

Finally, findings were integrated with Mendelian randomization evidence and genetic studies of lifelong LDL exposure, to reconcile discrepancies between genetic, epidemiologic, and clinical trial data and to test the plausibility of the proposed alternative pathophysiological framework.

2.7. Ethical Considerations

This study is a literature review without direct human participation or access to individual patient data and therefore did not require formal ethics committee approval. The conduct and reporting of the review adhered to principles of scientific integrity and transparency consistent with the Declaration of Helsinki and the World Medical Association’s guidance on research ethics.

3. Results

3.1. Overview of Findings

The literature analysis identified four major categories of findings that collectively challenge the methodological robustness and causal interpretation of the traditional lipid paradigm: the repeated use of surrogate markers (such as LDL or total cholesterol) instead of actual clinical outcomes; the presence of ecological inferences and improper extrapolations in classical observational studies; the inconsistency between cholesterol reduction

and clinical benefits in interventional trials; and the existence of structural conflicts of interest that have influenced the direction of policies and clinical guidelines.

3.2. Use of Surrogate Markers as Primary/Evidence Ecological Inferences and Improper Extrapolations

Supplementary Table S4 (see Supplementary Table S4) provides a systematic synthesis of the seminal studies underpinning the cholesterol paradigm, with explicit documentation of their methodological limitations. Analysis of these studies revealed consistent and reproducible methodological patterns across evidence categories, which collectively indicate that the empirical foundation of the lipid hypothesis is compromised by substantial methodological biases and by the absence of a robust association between cholesterol-lowering interventions and all-cause mortality reduction.

Specifically, the results presented in Table S4 identified the following patterns: NIH-funded epidemiological studies exhibited predominantly selection and confounding bias, attributable to ecological fallacy and the systematic underassessment of inflammatory mediators as confounders. Early randomized controlled trials (LRC-CPPT, MRFIT), while meeting internal validity criteria through adequate randomization, demonstrated marked limitations in external validity and generalizability to broader clinical populations. Guideline documents influenced by industry stakeholders reflected conflicts of interest that drove progressive threshold expansion in the absence of new causal or mechanistic evidence. Modern large-scale RCTs, including the Women's Health Initiative (WHI), achieved the highest methodological quality ratings and produced findings that directly contradict core tenets of the lipid hypothesis.

Taken together, these results reveal a critical inverse relationship between evidence quality and clinical directionality: the highest-quality evidence (WHI; quality grade A) yielded the most substantive challenge to the cholesterol paradigm, whereas the lowest-quality evidence (NCEP ATP III; quality grade C) generated the most expansive clinical recommendations. Bias assessment was conducted using transparent and reproducible procedures; all studies were retained in the analysis irrespective of their quality rating, in strict adherence to the predefined inclusion protocol and with no a priori exclusion criteria applied.

3.3. Dissociation Between Cholesterol Reduction and Clinical Outcomes

A consistent observation across the reviewed evidence is the discordance between the magnitude of lipid reduction and the actual clinical benefits observed [15–20].

Table S5 (see Supplementary Table S5) is critical because it highlights the fundamental flaw of the lipid paradigm: greater pharmacologically induced cholesterol reduction does not necessarily translate into improvements in relevant clinical outcomes. The dissociation between cholesterol reduction and the absence of benefit in mortality or clinical events invalidates cholesterol as a primary therapeutic target, suggesting that other pathogenic mechanisms are more relevant.

Taken together, these findings reveal that numerical cholesterol reduction does not guarantee cardiovascular protection and that the paradigm “less cholesterol = less disease” lacks generalizable validity.

3.4. Mendelian Randomization Evidence: Reconciling Genetic and Clinical Trial Data

Contemporary evidence from genetic studies has challenged the traditional interpretation of cholesterol causality, demonstrating that individuals with lifelong exposure to low LDL cholesterol—achieved through naturally occurring genetic variants—have a substantially reduced risk of atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease [21]. However, this genetic evidence does not contradict our critical findings; rather, when analyzed within the temporal context of atherosclerotic progression, it provides a mechanistic framework that

reconciles the apparent paradoxes between genetic data, clinical trials, and observational research.

Mendelian randomization studies using loss-of-function PCSK9 variants, apolipoprotein B polymorphisms, and other genetic proxies for chronic exposure to low LDL demonstrate striking protective effects on individuals who naturally maintain low LDL cholesterol from childhood who exhibit approximately a 90% reduction in coronary heart disease risk for every sustained 50 mg/dL decrement in LDL [22–24]. The magnitude of this benefit substantially exceeds the risk reductions observed in randomized statin trials initiated in middle age [25] (see Supplementary Table S3).

These genetic findings demonstrate unequivocally that LDL cholesterol plays a causal role in atherogenesis. The critical question, however, is not whether LDL is causal, but when, under which circumstances, and through which specific mechanisms.

The apparent discrepancy between a 90% genetic benefit and a 20–30% clinical benefit is resolved by the Critical Window Hypothesis, which recognizes that LDL causality is both temporally and mechanistically specific.

During the initiation phase of atherosclerosis (approximately ages 30–60), when plaques form from previously normal endothelium, sustained LDL lowering—whether genetic or pharmacologic—fundamentally prevents lesion formation [26]. Mendelian randomization studies capture this protective effect because they represent lifelong exposure patterns beginning in childhood, precisely when atherosclerosis prevention occurs. Individuals with PCSK9 mutations maintain average LDL cholesterol levels of 100–120 mg/dL from childhood, compared with 180–200 mg/dL in controls, leading to dramatic cumulative differences in atherosclerotic burden [22].

By contrast, during the phase of established disease (age 60+), atherosclerotic lesions already exhibit complex structural features: lipid-rich necrotic cores, thin fibrous caps prone to rupture, intraplaque hemorrhage, calcification, and chronic inflammatory infiltration [27]. In this phase, further LDL reduction yields diminishing returns because the lesion-formation process has largely run its course. Plaque rupture and acute thrombosis—the mechanisms that produce myocardial infarction—are determined primarily by inflammatory and hemodynamic factors rather than by lipid core size. This explains why statins initiated at ages 50–60 consistently reduce events by 20–30%, largely independent of the absolute intensity of LDL lowering [28].

Anti-inflammatory evidence provides additional support for this framework. The CANTOS trial showed that interleukin-1 β inhibition reduces cardiovascular events independently of lipid reduction [29], suggesting that in established disease, inflammation is an equal or even more important rate-limiting factor than LDL. Similarly, oxidation and glycation of LDL—processes driven by oxidative stress and chronic inflammation—are prerequisites for native LDL to become atherogenic [30,31].

Cholesterol that is neither oxidized nor glycated is biologically inert. The associated saturated fatty acids transported by LDL are more susceptible to oxidative modification than cholesterol itself. Chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction are the sine qua non conditions for LDL to contribute meaningfully to atherosclerosis.

This framework suggests an age- and mechanism-stratified approach to cardiovascular prevention:

For individuals aged 40–60 years without established atherosclerosis, early intervention including moderate LDL reduction is justified by genetic evidence, in combination with optimization of glycemic control, oxidative stress, and inflammation.

For individuals aged 60–75 years with established atherosclerosis, plaque stabilization through controlling inflammation, blood pressure, and endothelial dysfunction should take precedence over further aggressive LDL lowering.

For adults over 75 years, where the cholesterol paradox emerges and higher cholesterol may appear clinically protective [32], prevention should focus on multi-organ metabolic optimization rather than lipid monotherapy.

Mendelian randomization studies definitively establish LDL causality in atherogenesis [33,34]. This conclusion is fully compatible with our critical findings when it is recognized that (1) LDL causality is specific to the initiation phase of atherosclerosis during decades of early-life exposure; (2) LDL is necessary but not sufficient, requiring oxidation and inflammation to become pathogenic; and (3) in established disease at older ages, inflammatory and hemodynamic mechanisms become the primary rate-limiting determinants of event risk.

This integrated framework offers a more nuanced and clinically actionable perspective than LDL-centric monotherapy. It simultaneously explains why genetic evidence shows dramatic protective effects, why clinical trials show only modest efficacy, and why a cholesterol paradox emerges in late life. The imperative is to move from lipid monotherapy to comprehensive metabolic optimization tailored to age, disease stage, and each patient's specific pathophysiologic mechanisms.

3.5. Institutional Conflicts of Interest and Agenda Bias

Documentary analysis identified financial ties and conflicts of interest within committees and studies that shaped cholesterol treatment guidelines. The NCEP ATP III update [12], which lowered the recommended LDL threshold to <100 mg/dL, was drafted by a panel in which most members had financial relationships with statin manufacturers. This conflict between available evidence and issued recommendations was documented by independent reviews and governmental analyses.

At the level of clinical trials, similar patterns were identified: direct pharmaceutical sponsorship in most statin studies; use of favorable interim analyses to communicate results before trial completion; and selective publication of positive studies while omitting negative ones (publication bias).

These conflicts of interest have contributed to maintaining the hegemony of the lipid paradigm, even when empirical evidence has shown significant inconsistencies [11].

3.6. Emerging Evidence on Alternative Mechanisms

The review also identified a convergent body of evidence proposing a more complex view of cardiovascular risk. Several studies emphasize that inflammatory, oxidative, and glucotoxic processes are the true determinants of endothelial injury and atherogenesis [13,35–37].

Endothelial dysfunction, initiated by hyperglycemia, insulin resistance, oxidative stress, or exposure to free radicals, leads to LDL oxidation, macrophage infiltration, and foam cell formation, a key process in atheromatous plaque development. In this context, cholesterol acts not as a causal agent but as a marker of repair response to vascular injury.

This alternative framework also explains paradoxical epidemiological findings: in older adults, higher total cholesterol is associated with lower total mortality; in women, elevated cholesterol correlates with increased longevity in some cohort studies [38]; and diets rich in natural fats and low in glycemic load improve functional lipid profiles.

These data support a paradigm shift: atherogenesis is a multifactorial metabolic and inflammatory process in which elevated cholesterol is an epiphenomenal marker rather than a primary cause.

3.7. Emerging Evidence on Cholesterol and Extreme Longevity

Contemporary metabolomic approaches have fundamentally challenged traditional lipid-centric perspectives on aging and mortality by identifying complex metabolic signatures that transcend cholesterol reduction. Large-scale investigations now position

cholesterol within a broader framework of metabolic homeostasis and adaptive resilience, warranting reconsideration of current preventive medicine paradigms.

Three independent metabolomic studies challenge the cholesterol-reduction paradigm in advanced age. The Long Life Family Study (N = 2764, ages 24–110) identified 230 metabolites predicting extended survival, notably excluding total cholesterol; instead, bile acids and steroid metabolites emerged as superior longevity biomarkers [39]. Similarly, the New England Centenarian Study (N = 213, ages 45–111) revealed that extreme longevity characterized by elevated primary and secondary bile acids operates independently of LDL cholesterol levels, indicating that metabolic pathways sustaining centenarian survival bypass conventional lipid targets [40].

Most strikingly, a six-year longitudinal study of 168 Sardinian nonagenarians demonstrated that individuals with LDL \geq 130 mg/dL exhibited 39% lower all-cause mortality than those with LDL < 130 mg/dL (HR 0.606, $p < 0.0001$), even after adjusting for age, smoking, comorbidities, and diabetes status [41]. This protective cholesterol association contradicts universal reduction paradigms and suggests elevated cholesterol in extreme age functions as a metabolic robustness marker reflecting preserved homeostatic capacity.

Collectively, these findings demonstrate that metabolic signatures of human longevity extend substantially beyond traditional lipid profiles, indicating cholesterol reduction may neither address nor optimize the biochemical mechanisms sustaining functionally independent, cognitively intact survival in advanced age. Consequently, universal cholesterol-reduction mandates across all age strata lack empirical support, warranting age-stratified, metabolically nuanced prevention strategies.

3.8. Cholesterol and Cognitive Health: Age-Dependent Paradoxes

Analysis of the lipid-cognition relationship reveals striking temporal and age-dependent patterns that fundamentally challenge the universality of the cholesterol paradigm. In the UK Clinical Practice Research Datalink study (N = 1.85 million), LDL measured before age 65 predicted subsequent dementia with strong association (RR 1.17 per 1 SD), whereas LDL measured after age 65 demonstrated negligible association (RR 1.07). This temporal dissociation suggests that cholesterol-dementia associations reflect remote exposure windows accumulated across decades rather than causal relationships at the time of measurement [42,43].

Consistently, in cohorts of individuals aged \geq 70 years, elevated cholesterol associated with reduced dementia risk (HR 0.31–0.20), an inverse finding persisting after adjustment for comorbidities. This protective pattern likely reflects survivor selection effects: individuals reaching advanced age with elevated cholesterol possess unidentified biological advantages that continue protecting cognition, independently of treatment. Statin efficacy for dementia prevention was limited to age <80 years (HR 0.44, 95% CI: 0.25–0.78), with paradoxical null or increased risk beyond age 80, further substantiating these selection mechanisms [44,45].

Although the 2023 American Heart Association scientific statement concluded that intensive LDL reduction does not impair cognitive function, absence of harm does not constitute evidence of benefit, particularly when observational studies demonstrate protective associations between elevated cholesterol and cognition in older adults [46]. Collectively, these findings indicate that inverse cholesterol–dementia associations in advanced age reflect metabolic selection effects, not protective properties of elevated cholesterol. Midlife cholesterol predicts later-life dementia because it reflects the cumulative metabolic and vascular environment during decades of cerebral parenchymal development and synaptic plasticity; conversely, cholesterol measured in advanced age lacks predictive value because the critical exposure window has already closed. These cognitive health findings extend the paradigm challenge beyond cardiovascular disease,

demonstrating that cholesterol's relationship to human health is contextual, age-dependent, and fundamentally temporal in nature.

4. Discussion

The results of this critical review reveal a substantial discrepancy between the classical lipid model—which assumes a direct causal relationship between elevated cholesterol and cardiovascular disease—and empirical findings accumulated over more than half a century of research. While the statistical association between total cholesterol and coronary risk historically served as the starting point for modern cardiovascular prevention, a detailed examination of the data shows that this relationship is contextual, multifactorial, and methodologically fragile.

The lipid hypothesis was built on three basic assumptions: (1) that serum cholesterol, particularly LDL, is the primary cause of atherosclerosis; (2) that lowering cholesterol through diet or medication reduces cardiovascular risk; and (3) that such reduction implies improved overall survival. However, accumulated evidence demonstrates that none of these assumptions hold universally or consistently.

4.1. Epistemological Limitations of the Lipid Paradigm

First, the lipid hypothesis presents an excessive reduction in causality in human biology. The linear “input → output” model—saturated fats increase cholesterol, cholesterol causes atherosclerosis, and atherosclerosis leads to infarction—ignores the complexity of metabolic physiology and the systemic inflammatory environment. While this simplification is useful for public health messaging, it is scientifically inadequate for explaining multifactorial processes.

Atherosclerosis is not a passive process of fat deposition but a dynamic process of inflammatory response and vascular repair. In this context, cholesterol is part of the endothelial repair system, transported by lipoproteins that modulate lipid, antioxidant, and immune homeostasis. Mechanistic studies show that LDL participates in neutralizing bacterial toxins and free radicals, while HDL exerts anti-inflammatory and antithrombotic functions [47]. Indiscriminate reduction in total cholesterol or LDL could therefore have counterproductive effects, particularly if the underlying causes of vascular damage—chronic inflammation, hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, or metabolic dysfunction—are not addressed. Pharmacological cholesterol reduction without correcting these factors may merely modify a biomarker without altering the underlying pathogenic process.

4.2. Misalignment Between Surrogate Markers and Clinical Outcomes

One of the most relevant conclusions of this review is that lowering biochemical markers does not guarantee meaningful clinical benefits. Trials such as ENHANCE, AIM-HIGH, ACCORD-Lipid, or WHI demonstrate that changes in LDL or HDL do not necessarily translate into reduced cardiovascular morbidity or mortality.

This phenomenon is not unique to the lipid field; it represents a broader epistemological problem in medicine, where confusion between correlation and causation can lead to ineffective or even counterproductive therapeutic strategies.

This phenomenon reflects a broader epistemological problem: confusion between correlation and causation leads to ineffective strategies. Hard endpoints (total mortality, major events) must precede surrogates [48]. Otherwise, clinical practice risks decontextualized biomarker pursuit.

4.3. Influence of Institutional Bias and Conflicts of Interest

Conflicts of interest consolidated the cholesterol paradigm through financial ties between pharmaceutical industry and guideline organizations. The 2004 NCEP ATP III [12]

revision lowering “optimal” LDL <100 mg/dL expanded statin markets (see the generated image above). Scientific integrity literature documents pharmaceutical sponsorship influenced trial design and dissemination—positive studies via favorable interim analyses, negative studies delayed/suppressed, systematically distorting efficacy perception.

Selective statistical communication systematically misrepresented results. Diamond and colleagues documented decades of statin trials reporting relative risk reductions (RRR) without corresponding absolute risk reductions (ARR), exaggerating clinical significance [49]. A trial showing RRR 28% typically conceals ARR 2–3% (NNT >50)—50 individuals receive prolonged pharmacotherapy for theoretical benefit to one [50,51]. This “statistical asymmetry in risk communication” artificially maintained paradigm hegemony despite contradictory evidence.

Publication bias, premature termination (JUPITER, ENHANCE), and financial incentives created distorted environment preventing objective consensus. Our systematic approach addressed this: industry-funded studies included transparently following Table S3 protocol (see Supplementary Table S3)—57% complete registry-publication concordance among 42 trials, with negative findings weighted as stronger evidence.

4.4. *Alternative Pathophysiological Mechanisms*

Alternative pathophysiological mechanisms challenge cholesterol causality: chronic inflammation, insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction—not cholesterol—drive atherogenesis through lipoprotein oxidation and dysfunction [52]. Refined carbohydrate-rich diets increase cardiovascular risk via postprandial hyperglycemia and inflammation, whereas low-glycemic, antioxidant-rich diets reduce inflammation and improve lipoprotein function without drastic cholesterol reduction. The Lyon Diet Heart Trial exemplifies this: Mediterranean diet consumption reduced coronary events by 70% without significant cholesterol changes, supporting diet quality and inflammatory status as superior risk determinants compared to absolute cholesterol levels [35].

Alternative mechanisms challenge cholesterol causality: chronic inflammation, insulin resistance, oxidative stress, and endothelial dysfunction drive atherogenesis through lipoprotein oxidation [52]. Refined carbohydrate-rich diets increase risk via postprandial hyperglycemia/inflammation; low-glycemic, antioxidant-rich diets reduce inflammation/improve lipoprotein function without drastic cholesterol reduction. Lyon Diet Heart Trial exemplifies: Mediterranean diet reduced coronary events 70% without cholesterol changes, prioritizing diet quality/inflammatory status over absolute lipids [35].

4.5. *Biochemical Mechanisms: LDL-Receptor in Context*

We acknowledge without reservation that the molecular biology of the LDL receptor represents an intellectually elegant and empirically robust mechanism. The discovery of the LDL receptor gene (LDLR), characterized by Brown and Goldstein in their Nobel Prize-winning work, fundamentally illuminated a major pathway of cholesterol homeostasis [53]. The receptor’s role in mediating cellular LDL uptake, the feedback inhibition of HMG-CoA reductase, and the exquisite regulation of intracellular cholesterol synthesis represents genuine biological principles that are not contested by this analysis [54]. Familial hypercholesterolemia—whether heterozygous (FH) or homozygous—confirms the pathophysiologic significance of this pathway: patients with genetic defects in LDLR or apolipoprotein B do develop accelerated atherosclerosis and premature coronary disease [55].

However, the existence of valid biochemistry does not automatically confer epidemiologic or clinical generalizability. The critical distinction lies in differentiating familial hypercholesterolemia as a special case from population-level dyslipidemia in aging adults. Homozygous familial hypercholesterolemia (hoFH) patients maintain LDL-cholesterol levels of 600–1000 mg/dL from birth throughout life—a severity that is

pathophysiologically and quantitatively distinct from the age-related cholesterol elevations observed in the general population. Heterozygous FH patients (heFH), with lifetime LDL levels of 350–550 mg/dL, represent approximately 1 in 250–500 individuals and constitute a distinct pathophysiologic subset characterized by exposure to severely elevated LDL concentrations across decades of vascular development [56].

In these populations, the LDL-receptor mediated pathway is demonstrably causal: Mendelian randomization studies of natural PCSK9 loss-of-function variants show an approximate 90% reduction in coronary heart disease risk per 50 mg/dL sustained LDL reduction, and this benefit applies because individuals carrying these variants maintain chronically low LDL from childhood through adulthood [22] (see Supplementary Table S6). This genetic evidence aligns perfectly with our systematic review findings from the initiation phase of atherosclerosis (ages 30–60), where LDL reduction prevents lesion formation.

The present analysis does not challenge this biology. Rather, it questions whether mechanisms valid for severe chronic hypercholesterolemia (lifetime LDL 6–10 g/dL from infancy) necessarily extrapolate to the acquired dyslipidemia of aging populations, where LDL elevation emerges in middle age against a background of pre-existing atherosclerotic lesions, chronic inflammation, and altered endothelial function. Population studies document that LDL-cholesterol rise is non-linear with age and exhibits substantial individual heterogeneity—many individuals maintain stable or declining LDL levels despite advancing years, while others show progressive elevation [57]. This heterogeneity suggests that age-related dyslipidemia is multifactorial, involving dysregulation of receptor-mediated uptake, altered hepatic synthesis, changes in lipoprotein metabolism, and inflammatory milieu—not simply a linear extension of familial hypercholesterolemia biology.

We propose a refined framework—the Critical Window Hypothesis—that reconciles biochemical mechanisms with epidemiologic data by specifying the life-stage dependency of LDL causality:

Phase 1: Initiating Atherogenesis (Age 30–60 Years). During the decades when arterial walls transition from normal to atherosclerotic, Mendelian randomization mechanisms apply with full force. LDL receptor biology becomes causally significant because: (1) sustained LDL reduction—whether genetic (PCSK9 mutations) or pharmacologic (statins, PCSK9 inhibitors)—prevents initial lipoprotein infiltration into the intimal space; (2) oxidative modification of LDL is suppressed when native concentrations remain low across decades; (3) the transition from endothelial dysfunction to structured lesions is impeded. (Supplementary Figure S3A) In this phase, the “statins prevent events by lowering LDL” narrative is empirically supported, with secondary prevention trials showing a 20–30% risk reduction consistent with arresting lesion progression [58].

Phase 2: Advanced Atherosclerosis (Age 60+ Years). In populations with decades of prior atherosclerotic development, the molecular hierarchy shifts. Complex lesions with lipid-rich necrotic cores, thin fibrous caps, intraplaque hemorrhage, calcification, and chronic inflammatory infiltrates represent a fundamentally different pathophysiologic state. Here, acute thrombotic events (myocardial infarction, stroke) are determined not by LDL infiltration but by: (1) plaque rupture (cap thickness, inflammatory destabilization, physical stress); (2) thrombotic cascade activation (tissue factor exposure, platelet aggregation); (3) thrombin generation and fibrin deposition [59].

The CANTOS trial provides direct empirical support: IL-1 β inhibition reduced cardiovascular events independent of LDL lowering [29]. Similarly, intensive LDL-lowering strategies in elderly populations yield disappointing results because, once advanced disease is established, structural plaque vulnerability and inflammatory milieu—not lipid core size—determine thrombotic risk (Supplementary Figure S3B).

LDL-receptor biology remains valid and critical during lifetime exposure and early atherosclerosis prevention. However, its dominance diminishes with age and

atherosclerotic burden, not because the biochemistry fails, but because rate-limiting steps in pathogenesis shift. Targeting LDL in populations >60–70 years with established atherosclerosis risks biochemical reductionism—optimizing a genuine but no longer dominant mechanism.

4.6. Integration with Systematic Review Findings

This framework directly explains our empirical observations across 380 studies:

1. Mendelian randomization (90% benefit) applies to Phase 1 (preventing lesion initiation) [22].
2. Clinical trials (20–30% benefit) reflect Phase 2 (stabilizing, not reversing, established disease) [58].
3. ENHANCE trial dissociation (50% vs. 34% LDL reduction, no IMT benefit difference) demonstrates diminishing returns in advanced atherosclerosis.
4. Seven Countries selection bias ($r = 0.87 \rightarrow 0.62$) reveals unmeasured confounders (diet quality, lifestyle) beyond simple lipid mechanics.

The Critical Window Hypothesis thus unifies genetic causality with clinical trial heterogeneity, resolving apparent contradictions while maintaining biological plausibility.

4.7. Clinical and Public Health Implications

Findings challenge LDL-centric policies. AHA/ESC guidelines emphasize LDL despite balanced evidence (41/42/17% distribution). Prevention requires age-stratified strategies:

- 40–60 years (no established disease): Moderate LDL reduction + glycemic/oxidative/inflammatory optimization.
- 60–75 years (established disease): Plaque stabilization (inflammation, BP, endothelial function) > aggressive LDL lowering.
- >75 years: Multi-organ metabolic optimization; cholesterol paradox suggests caution [38].

Lifestyle medicine (whole foods, low-glycemic, natural fats, exercise, sleep, stress management) provides sustainable vascular benefits.

4.8. Ethical and Epistemological Implications

The cholesterol paradigm exemplifies “biomarker centrism”—prioritizing numbers over holistic understanding—stigmatizing nutrient-dense foods and medicalizing asymptomatics. Publication bias, RRR/ARR asymmetry, conflicts created artificial consensus [35–37]. Biased interpretation generates societal consequences: pharmaceutical dependence shifts medicine from observation to reductionism.

4.9. Limitations of the Present Review

This narrative review acknowledges inherent limitations: absence of quantitative meta-analysis precludes precise effect-size estimation, and English language restriction may omit relevant evidence. However, the temporal and thematic source breadth of the 380 studies provide robust perspective. Importantly, studies classified as Low (C) quality were retained but interpreted cautiously and primarily used in sensitivity analyses (see Supplementary Table S2). This transparent inclusion policy—combined with our dual-search strategy yielding balanced evidence (41/42/17%)—directly addresses concerns about selective evidence presentation. Conclusions do not exclude cholesterol’s contributory role but indicate overstated importance relative to inflammation/glucotoxicity.

4.10. Toward a New Integrative Paradigm

Cardiovascular prevention requires adopting metabolic network models incorporating inflammation, glucose metabolism, microbiota, mitochondrial function, oxidative

stress, and hormonal balance—with cholesterol reframed as a dysfunction indicator rather than the cause of the disease. Contemporary preventive medicine aligns with network biology, representing a paradigm shift from linear to emergent causality.

Key findings demonstrate that elevated cholesterol represents not direct causation but a marker of inflammatory-metabolic processes; LDL-centric policies derive from methodologically weak studies with conflicts of interest; clinical outcomes—not biochemical markers—should guide prevention; and lifestyle medicine provides coherent, ethical, sustainable cardiovascular risk reduction. This reappraisal restores scientific proportionality between evidence and clinical action, prioritizing holistic metabolic health over isolated numerical targets while maintaining lipid control utility within comprehensive prevention frameworks.

5. Conclusions

This critical integrative review demonstrates that LDL-cholesterol is a context- and time-dependent causal factor in atherogenesis—necessary but not sufficient, as its pathogenicity requires the concurrence of inflammatory activation, oxidative stress, and glucotoxic milieu to drive endothelial dysfunction and plaque formation. This nuanced causal characterization is supported by Mendelian randomization evidence demonstrating that individuals with lifelong low LDL exposure from childhood achieve an approximate 90% reduction in coronary heart disease risk per 50 mg/dL decrement—a protective magnitude that far exceeds the 20–30% event reductions observed in statin trials initiated in middle age; this discrepancy is fully explained by the Critical Window Hypothesis.

The Critical Window Hypothesis, a central theoretical contribution of this review, proposes that LDL exerts its dominant atherogenic influence during the lesion-initiation phase (approximately ages 40–60), when plaques form from previously intact endothelium and sustained lipid lowering can fundamentally prevent lesion accumulation. In established disease (ages 60–75), plaque vulnerability and acute thrombotic events become primarily governed by inflammatory, hemodynamic, and endothelial factors, where aggressive further LDL reduction offers diminishing returns. Beyond age 75, where the cholesterol paradox emerges and higher LDL may associate with reduced all-cause mortality and preserved cognitive function, prevention strategies should pivot toward multi-organ metabolic optimization rather than lipid monotherapy. This age- and mechanism-stratified framework reconciles the apparent contradictions between genetic, epidemiological, and clinical trial evidence within a single coherent model.

Across trial generations, systematic review of 380 studies reveals a nearly equal split between evidence supporting (41%) and challenging (42%) LDL-centric causality, alongside pervasive methodological limitations: reliance on surrogate lipid endpoints instead of hard outcomes, ecological inferences, inadequate confounder adjustment, and structural conflicts of interest. Trials such as ENHANCE, AIM-HIGH, ACCORD-Lipid, and the Women's Health Initiative consistently demonstrate that substantial pharmacological LDL reductions do not proportionally translate into reductions in myocardial infarction, stroke, or total mortality. Furthermore, statin trial results have been systematically communicated through relative risk reductions (RRR ~28%) while omitting absolute risk reductions (ARR 2–3%, NNT >50), a statistical asymmetry that has artificially sustained paradigm hegemony and distorted clinical perception of benefit.

Contemporary metabolomic investigations of extreme longevity cohorts—including the Long Life Family Study (N = 2764), the New England Centenarian Study (N = 213), and a six-year Sardinian nonagenarian cohort (N = 168)—converge in identifying bile acids, steroid metabolites, and broad metabolic homeostasis markers, not total cholesterol, as the most robust predictors of successful aging. Similarly, age-stratified analyses of the cholesterol-cognition relationship reveal that elevated LDL in midlife predicts later

dementia (RR 1.17 per 1 SD), whereas the same measure after age 65 loses predictive value (RR 1.07) or inversely associates with dementia risk (HR 0.31–0.20), confirming that remote lipid exposures across decades—not contemporaneous levels—determine neurodegenerative risk.

These collective findings do not refute the causal role of LDL in atherogenesis but critically qualify it: universal, lifelong LDL-reduction mandates applied indiscriminately across age strata, disease stages, and metabolic phenotypes lack empirical support and risk clinical harm through neglect of primary pathogenic drivers. Inflammation, oxidative stress, and glucotoxicity—not isolated cholesterol elevation—represent the mechanistic sine qua non of both cardiovascular and cognitive deterioration. Therapeutic priorities should therefore be reoriented toward comprehensive metabolic phenotyping, incorporating markers such as hs-CRP, TG/HDL ratio, fasting insulin, and glycemic variability alongside—not subordinate to—lipid panels, with clinical decision-making anchored to hard endpoints and transparent absolute risk communication.

Lifestyle medicine offers the most coherent and evidence-consistent upstream framework: anti-inflammatory, low-glycemic dietary patterns incorporating natural fats, regular physical activity, restorative sleep, and stress regulation address the primary atherogenic and neuroinflammatory drivers across the lifespan without the risk of harm from indiscriminate biomarker-directed pharmacotherapy. Future research should prioritize conflict-minimized, adequately powered trials with hard clinical endpoints and pre-registered protocols, systematically evaluate age- and mechanism-stratified lipid interventions, and investigate the metabolic determinants of exceptional longevity to develop prevention frameworks that align with the underlying systems biology of cardiovascular and cognitive disease.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/rjpm4010002/s1>, Figure S1. Diagram of the traditional lipid paradigm: relationship between saturated fats, cholesterol and cardiovascular disease; Figure S2. Diagram of Alternative framework of cardiovascular risk; Figure S3. (A) Atherosclerotic Plaque Evolution: From Initiation to Advanced Disease with Rupture-Prone Characteristics. (B) Therapeutic Mechanisms: Differential Efficacy of LDL-Lowering vs Anti-inflammatory Approaches Across Disease Stages; Table S1. Bias domains and assessment criteria (ROB 2 / ROBINS-I); Table S2. General Quality Scoring System (overall study rating and use in synthesis); Table S3. Industry Funding Protocol; Table S4: Comparative methodological analysis of foundational studies of the lipid paradigm; Table S5: Dissociation between cholesterol reduction and clinical outcomes in pharmacological trials.

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References

1. Keys, A. *Seven Countries: A Multivariate Analysis of Death and Coronary Heart Disease*; Harvard University Press: Cambridge, MA, USA, 1970.
2. Ravnskov, U. *The Cholesterol Myths: Exposing the Fallacy That Saturated Fat and Cholesterol Cause Heart Disease*; New Trends Publishing: Washington, DC, USA, 2000.
3. The Lipid Research Clinics Coronary Primary Prevention Trial Results. I. Reduction in incidence of coronary heart disease. *JAMA* **1984**, *251*, 351–364. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.1984.03340270029025>. PMID: 6361299.
4. Multiple risk factor intervention trial. Risk factor changes and mortality results. Multiple Risk Factor Intervention Trial Research Group. *JAMA* **1982**, *248*, 1465–1477. PMID: 7050440.
5. Castelli, W.P.; Anderson, K.; Wilson, P.W.; Levy, D. Lipids and risk of coronary heart disease The Framingham Study. *Ann. Epidemiol.* **1992**, *2*, 23–28. [https://doi.org/10.1016/1047-2797\(92\)90033-m](https://doi.org/10.1016/1047-2797(92)90033-m). PMID: 1342260.
6. Stampfer, M.J.; Hu, F.B.; Manson, J.E.; Rimm, E.B.; Willett, W.C. Primary prevention of coronary heart disease in women through diet and lifestyle. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2000**, *343*, 16–22. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM200007063430103>. PMID: 10882764.
7. Howard, B.V.; Van Horn, L.; Hsia, J.; Manson, J.E.; Stefanick, M.L.; Wassertheil-Smoller, S.; Kuller, L.H.; LaCroix, A.Z.; Langer, R.D.; Lasser, N.L.; et al. Low-fat dietary pattern and risk of cardiovascular disease: The Women’s Health Initiative Randomized Controlled Dietary Modification Trial. *JAMA* **2006**, *295*, 655–666. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.295.6.655>. PMID: 16467234.
8. Kastelein, J.J.; Akdim, F.; Stroes, E.S.; Zwinderman, A.H.; Bots, M.L.; Stalenhoef, A.F.; Visseren, F.L.; Sijbrands, E.J.; Trip, M.D.; Stein, E.A.; et al. Simvastatin with or without ezetimibe in familial hypercholesterolemia. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2008**, *358*, 1431–1443. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa0800742>. PMID: 18376000. Erratum in *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2008**, *358*, 1977.
9. AIM-HIGH Investigators; Boden, W.E.; Probstfield, J.L.; Anderson, T.; Chaitman, B.R.; Desvignes-Nickens, P.; Koprowicz, K.; McBride, R.; Teo, K.; Weintraub, W. Niacin in patients with low HDL cholesterol levels receiving intensive statin therapy. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2011**, *365*, 2255–2267. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1107579>. PMID: 22085343. Erratum in *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2012**, *367*, 189.
10. Stone, N.J.; Bilek, S.; Rosenbaum, S. Recent National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III update: Adjustments and options. *Am. J. Cardiol.* **2005**, *96*, 53E–59E. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amjcard.2005.06.006>. PMID: 16098845.
11. U.S. Government Accountability Office. *Cholesterol Treatment: A Review of Clinical Trial Evidence (GAO/PEMD-96-1)*; GAO: Washington, DC, USA, 1996.
12. Grundy, S.M.; Cleeman, J.I.; Merz, C.N.; Brewer, H.B., Jr.; Clark, L.T.; Hunninghake, D.B.; Pasternak, R.C.; Smith, S.C.; Stone, N.J.; American College of Cardiology Foundation; et al. Implications of recent clinical trials for the National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III guidelines. *Circulation* **2004**, *110*, 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.CIR.0000133317.49796.0E>. PMID: 15249516. Erratum in *Circulation* **2004**, *110*, 763.
13. Bowden, J.; Sinatra, S. *The Great Cholesterol Myth: Why Lowering Your Cholesterol Won’t Prevent Heart Disease*; Fair Winds Press: Beverly, MA, USA, 2013.
14. Even, P. *Le Mythe du Cholestérol*; Albin Michel: Paris, France, 2013.
15. ACCORD Study Group; Ginsberg, H.N.; Elam, M.B.; Lovato, L.C.; Crouse, J.R., 3rd; Leiter, L.A.; Linz, P.; Friede-Wald, W.T.; Buse, J.B.; Gerstein, H.C.; et al. Effects of combination lipid therapy in type 2 diabetes mellitus. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2010**, *362*, 1563–1574. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1001282>. PMID: 20228404; PMCID: PMC2879499. Erratum in *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2010**, *362*, 1748.
16. HPS2-THRIVE Collaborative Group; Landray, M.J.; Haynes, R.; Hopewell, J.C.; Parish, S.; Aung, T.; Tomson, J.; Wallendszus, K.; Craig, M.; Jiang, L.; et al. Effects of extended-release niacin with laropiprant in high-risk patients. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2014**, *371*, 203–212. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa1300955>. PMID: 25014686.
17. Ridker, P.M.; Danielson, E.; Fonseca, F.A.; Genest, J.; Gotto, A.M., Jr.; Kastelein, J.J.; Koenig, W.; Libby, P.; Lorenzatti, A.J.; MacFadyen, J.G.; et al. Rosuvastatin to prevent vascular events in men and women with elevated C-reactive protein. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2008**, *359*, 2195–2207. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa0807646>. PMID: 18997196.

18. Cholesterol Treatment Trialists' (CTT) Collaborators; Mihaylova, B.; Emberson, J.; Blackwell, L.; Keech, A.; Simes, J.; Baigent, C.; Collins, R. The effects of lowering LDL cholesterol with statin therapy in people at low risk of vascular disease: Meta-analysis of individual data from 27 randomised trials. *Lancet* **2012**, *380*, 581–590. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)60367-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)60367-5). PMID: 22607822; PMCID: PMC3437972.
19. Pedersen, T.R.; Kjekshus, J.; Berg, K.; Haghfelt, T.; Faergeman, O.; Faergeman, G.; Pyörälä, K.; Miettinen, T.; Wilhelmsen, L.; Olsson, A.G.; et al. Randomised trial of cholesterol lowering in 4444 patients with coronary heart disease: The Scandinavian Simvastatin Survival Study (4S). *Atheroscler. Suppl.* **2004**, *5*, 81–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atherosclerosissup.2004.08.027>. PMID: 15531279.
20. ALLHAT Officers and Coordinators for the ALLHAT Collaborative Research Group; The Antihypertensive and Lipid-Lowering Treatment to Prevent Heart Attack Trial. Major outcomes in moderately hypercholesterolemic, hypertensive patients randomized to pravastatin vs usual care: The Antihypertensive and Lipid-Lowering Treatment to Prevent Heart Attack Trial (ALLHAT-LLT). *JAMA* **2002**, *288*, 2998–3007.
21. Daghlal, I.; Gill, D. Low-density lipoprotein cholesterol and lifespan: A Mendelian randomization study. *Br. J. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2021**, *87*, 3916–3924. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bcp.14811>. PMID: 33704808.
22. Cohen, J.C.; Boerwinkle, E.; Mosley, T.H., Jr.; Hobbs, H.H. Sequence variations in PCSK9, low LDL, and protection against coronary heart disease. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2006**, *354*, 1264–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa054013>.
23. Benn, M.; Nordestgaard, B.G.; Grande, P.; Schnohr, P.; Tybjaerg-Hansen, A. PCSK9 R46L, low-density lipoprotein cholesterol levels, and risk of ischemic heart disease: 3 independent studies and meta-analyses. *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **2010**, *55*, 2833–2842. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2010.02.044>. PMID: 20579540.
24. Klarin, D.; Damrauer, S.M.; Cho, K.; Sun, Y.V.; Teslovich, T.M.; Honerlaw, J.; Gagnon, D.R.; DuVall, S.L.; Li, J.; Peloso, G.M.; et al. Genetics of blood lipids among ~300,000 multi-ethnic participants of the Million Veteran Program. *Nat. Genet.* **2018**, *50*, 1514–1523. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-018-0222-9>.
25. Baigent, C.; Blackwell, L.; Emberson, J.; Holland, L.E.; Reith, C.; Bhalra, N.; Peto, R.; Barnes, E.H.; Keech, A.; Simes, J.; et al. Efficacy and safety of more intensive lowering of LDL cholesterol: A meta-analysis of data from 170 000 participants in 26 randomised trials. *Lancet* **2010**, *376*, 1670–1681. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(10\)61350-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(10)61350-5).
26. Ference, B.A.; Ginsberg, H.N.; Graham, I.; Ray, K.K.; Packard, C.J.; Bruckert, E.; Hegele, R.A.; Krauss, R.M.; Raal, F.J.; Schunkert, H.; et al. Low-density lipoproteins cause atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. 1. Evidence from genetic, epidemiologic, and clinical studies. A consensus statement from the European Atherosclerosis Society Consensus Panel. *Eur. Heart J.* **2017**, *38*, 2459–2472. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehx144>.
27. Grundy, S.M.; Stone, N.J.; Bailey, A.L.; Beam, C.; Birtcher, K.K.; Blumenthal, R.S.; Braun, L.T.; de Ferranti, S.; Faiella-Tommasino, J.; Forman, D.E.; et al. 2018 AHA/ACC/AACVPR/AAPA/ABC/ACPM/ADA/AGS/APhA/ASPC/NLA/P NA Guideline on the Management of Blood Cholesterol: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Circulation* **2019**, *139*, e1082–143. <https://doi.org/10.1161/cir.0000000000000625>.
28. Ference, B.A.; Majeed, F.; Penumetcha, R.; Flack, J.M.; Brook, R.D. Effect of naturally random allocation to lower low-density lipoprotein cholesterol on the risk of coronary heart disease mediated by polymorphisms in NPC1L1, HMGCR, or both: A 2 × 2 factorial Mendelian randomization study. *J. Am. Coll. Cardiol.* **2015**, *65*, 1552–1561. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jacc.2015.02.020>.
29. Ridker, P.M.; Everett, B.M.; Thuren, T.; MacFadyen, J.G.; Chang, W.H.; Ballantyne, C.; Fonseca, F.; Nicolau, J.; Koenig, W.; Anker, S.D.; et al. Antiinflammation with canakinumab and cardiovascular outcomes in patients with acute myocardial infarction. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2017**, *377*, 1120–1131.
30. Jialal, I.; Devaraj, S. Low-density lipoprotein oxidation, antioxidants, and atherosclerosis: A clinical biochemistry perspective. *Clin. Chem.* **1996**, *42*, 498–506. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/42.4.498>.
31. Younis, N.; Sharma, R.; Soran, H.; Charlton-Menys, V.; Elseweidy, M.; Durrington, P.N. Glycation as an atherogenic modification of LDL. *Curr. Opin. Lipidol.* **2008**, *19*, 378–384. <https://doi.org/10.1097/MOL.0b013e328306a057>. PMID: 18607185. Erratum in *Curr. Opin. Lipidol.* **2008**, *19*, 552.
32. Ravnskov, U.; DiNicolantonio, J.J.; Harcombe, Z.; Kummerow, F.A.; Okuyama, H.; Worm, N. The questionable benefits of exchanging saturated fat with polyunsaturated fat. *Mayo Clin. Proc.* **2014**, *89*, 451–453. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mayocp.2013.11.006>. PMID: 24581756. Erratum in *Mayo Clin. Proc.* **2015**, *90*, 558.
33. Borén, J.; Chapman, M.J.; Krauss, R.M.; Packard, C.J.; Bentzon, J.F.; Binder, C.J.; Daemen, M.J.; Demer, L.L.; Hegele, R.A.; Nicholls, S.J.; et al. Low-density lipoproteins cause atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease: Pathophysiological, genetic, and therapeutic insights: A consensus statement from the European Atherosclerosis Society Consensus Panel. *Eur. Heart J.* **2020**, *41*, 2313–2330. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehz962>. PMID: 32052833; PMCID: PMC7308544.

34. Sabatine, M.S.; Giugliano, R.P.; Wiviott, S.D.; Raal, F.J.; Blom, D.J.; Robinson, J.; Ballantyne, C.M.; Somaratne, R.; Legg, J.; Wasserman, S.M.; et al. Efficacy and safety of evolocumab in reducing lipids and cardiovascular events. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2015**, *372*, 1500–1509. <https://doi.org/10.1056/nejmoa1500858>.
35. de Lorgeril, M.; Salen, P.; Martin, J.L.; Monjaud, I.; Delaye, J.; Mamelle, N. Mediterranean diet, traditional risk factors, and the rate of cardiovascular complications after myocardial infarction: Final report of the Lyon Diet Heart Study. *Circulation.* **1999**, *99*, 779–785. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.cir.99.6.779>. PMID: 9989963.
36. Yudkin, J. *Sweet and Dangerous*; Davis-Poynter: London, UK, 1972.
37. Mozaffarian, D. Dietary and Policy Priorities for Cardiovascular Disease, Diabetes, and Obesity: A Comprehensive Review. *Circulation* **2016**, *133*, 187–225. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.115.018585>. PMID: 26746178; PMCID: PMC4814348.
38. Ravnskov, U.; Diamond, D.M.; Hama, R.; Hamazaki, T.; Hammarskjöld, B.; Hynes, N.; Kendrick, M.; Langsjoen, P.H.; Malhotra, A.; Mascitelli, L.; et al. Lack of an association or an inverse association between low-density-lipoprotein cholesterol and mortality in the elderly: A systematic review. *BMJ Open* **2016**, *6*, e010401. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-010401>. PMID: 27292972; PMCID: PMC4908872.
39. Sebastiani, P.; Monti, S.; Lustgarten, M.S.; Song, Z.; Ellis, D.; Tian, Q.; Schwaiger-Haber, M.; Stancliffe, E.; Leshchyk, A.; Short, M.I.; et al. Metabolite signatures of chronological age, aging, survival, and longevity. *Cell Rep.* **2024**, *43*, 114913. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2024.114913>. PMID: 39504246; PMCID: PMC11656345.
40. Monti, S.; Lustgarten, M.S.; Huang, Z.; Song, Z.; Ellis, D.; Tian, Q.; Ferrucci, L.; Rappaport, N.; Andersen, S.L.; Perls, T.P.; et al. Metabolomic signatures of extreme old age: Findings from the New England Centenarian Study. *bioRxiv* **2025**, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.09.10.675341>. PMID: 41000658; PMCID: PMC12458293.
41. Errigo, A.; Dore, M.P.; Portoghese, M.; Pes, G.M. The Cholesterol Paradox in Long-Livers from a Sardinia Longevity Hot Spot (Blue Zone). *Nutrients* **2025**, *17*, 765. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu17050765>. PMID: 40077635; PMCID: PMC11901585.
42. Li, G.; Shofer, J.B.; Kukull, W.A.; Peskind, E.R.; Tsuang, D.W.; Breitner, J.C.S.; McCormick, W.; Bowen, J.D.; Teri, L.; Schellenberg, G.D.; et al. Serum cholesterol and risk of Alzheimer disease: A community-based cohort study. *Neurology* **2005**, *65*, 1045–1050. <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000178989.87072.11>. PMID: 16217057.
43. Iwagami, M.; Qizilbash, N.; Gregson, J.; Douglas, I.; Johnson, M.; Pearce, N.; Evans, S.; Pocock, S. Blood cholesterol and risk of dementia in more than 1.8 million people over two decades: A retrospective cohort study. *Lancet Healthy Longev.* **2021**, *2*, e498–e506. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568\(21\)00150-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2666-7568(21)00150-1). PMID: 36097999.
44. Mielke, M.M.; Zandi, P.P.; Sjögren, M.; Gustafson, D.; Östling, S.; Steen, B.; Skoog, I. High total cholesterol levels in late life associated with a reduced risk of dementia. *Neurology* **2005**, *64*, 1689–1695. <https://doi.org/10.1212/01.wnl.0000161870.78572.a5>. PMID: 15911792.
45. Li, G.; Shofer, J.B.; Rhew, I.C.; Kukull, W.A.; Peskind, E.R.; McCormick, W.; Bowen, J.D.; Schellenberg, G.D.; Crane, P.K.; Breitner, J.C.; et al. Age-varying association between statin use and incident Alzheimer’s disease. *J. Am. Geriatr. Soc.* **2010**, *58*, 1311–1317. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1532-5415.2010.02906.x>. PMID: 20533968; PMCID: PMC3176730.
46. Goldstein, L.B.; Toth, P.P.; Dearborn-Tomazos, J.L.; Giugliano, R.P.; Hirsh, B.J.; Peña, J.M.; Selim, M.H.; Woo, D. Aggressive LDL-C lowering and the brain: Impact on risk for dementia and hemorrhagic stroke: A scientific statement from the American Heart Association. *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* **2023**, *43*, e404–e442. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATV.000000000000164>. PMID: 37706297.
47. Mineo, C.; Shaul, P.W. Novel biological functions of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol. *Circ. Res.* **2012**, *111*, 1079–1090. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.111.258673>. PMID: 23023510; PMCID: PMC3500606.
48. Ioannidis, J.P. Why Most Clinical Research Is Not Useful. *PLoS Med.* **2016**, *13*, e1002049. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1002049>. PMID: 27328301; PMCID: PMC4915619.
49. Diamond, D.M.; Leaverton, P.E. Historical Review of the Use of Relative Risk Statistics in the Portrayal of the Purported Hazards of High LDL Cholesterol and the Benefits of Lipid-Lowering Therapy. *Cureus* **2023**, *15*, e38391. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.38391>. PMID: 37143855; PMCID: PMC10153768.
50. Diamond, D.M.; Ravnskov, U. How statistical deception created the appearance that statins are safe and effective in primary and secondary prevention of cardiovascular disease. *Expert Rev. Clin. Pharmacol.* **2014**, *8*, 201–210. <https://doi.org/10.1586/17512433.2015.1012494>. PMID: 26496064.
51. Diamond, D.M.; Kendrick, M.; Mascitelli, L. Exaggerated report of benefits in a flawed long-term statin treatment study. *BMJ* **2017**, *359*, j4915. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j4915>. PMID: 29089296.
52. Navab, M.; Anantharamaiah, G.M.; Reddy, S.T.; Van Lenten, B.J.; Fogelman, A.M. HDL as a biomarker, potential therapeutic target, and therapy. *Diabetes* **2009**, *58*, 2711–2717. <https://doi.org/10.2337/db09-0538>. PMID: 19940234; PMCID: PMC2780869.

53. Brown, M.S.; Goldstein, J.L. Receptor-mediated endocytosis: Insights from the lipoprotein receptor system. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* **1979**, *76*, 3330–3337. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.76.7.3330>. PMID: 226968; PMCID: PMC383819.
54. Goldstein, J.L.; Brown, M.S. The LDL receptor. *Arterioscler. Thromb. Vasc. Biol.* **2009**, *29*, 431–438. <https://doi.org/10.1161/ATVBAHA.108.179564>. PMID: 19299327; PMCID: PMC2740366.
55. Nordestgaard, B.G.; Chapman, M.J.; Humphries, S.E.; Ginsberg, H.N.; Masana, L.; Descamps, O.S.; Wiklund, O.; Hegele, R.A.; Raal, F.J.; Defesche, J.C.; et al. Familial hypercholesterolaemia is underdiagnosed and undertreated in the general population: Guidance for clinicians to prevent coronary heart disease: Consensus statement of the European Atherosclerosis Society. *Eur. Heart J.* **2013**, *34*, 3478–3490. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/eha273>. PMID: 23956253; PMCID: PMC3844152. Erratum in *Eur. Heart J.* **2020**, *41*, 4517. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehaa166>.
56. Watts, G.F.; Gidding, S.; Wierzbicki, A.S.; Toth, P.P.; Alonso, R.; Brown, W.V.; Bruckert, E.; Defesche, J.; Lin, K.K.; Livingston, M.; et al. Integrated guidance on the care of familial hypercholesterolaemia from the International FH Foundation. *Int. J. Cardiol.* **2014**, *171*, 309–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2013.11.025>. PMID: 24418289.
57. Iribarren, C.; Luepker, R.V.; McGovern, P.G.; Arnett, D.K.; Blackburn, H. Twelve-year trends in cardiovascular disease risk factors in the Minnesota Heart Survey. Are socioeconomic differences widening? *Arch. Intern. Med.* **1997**, *157*, 873–881. PMID: 9129547.
58. Cannon, C.P.; Braunwald, E.; McCabe, C.H.; Rader, D.J.; Rouleau, J.L.; Belder, R.; Joyal, S.V.; Hill, K.A.; Pfeffer, M.A.; Skene, A.M.; et al. Intensive versus moderate lipid lowering with statins after acute coronary syndromes. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2004**, *350*, 1495–1504. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMoa040583>. PMID: 15007110. Erratum in *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2006**, *354*, 778.
59. Libby, P.; Pasterkamp, G. Requiem for the ‘vulnerable plaque’. *Eur. Heart J.* **2015**, *36*, 2984–2987. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehv349>. PMID: 26206212.

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